

DIGITAL INNOVATIONS IN THE MODERN WORLD: PREREQUISITES AND POSSIBILITIES OF USE

Yo'ldoshev Ozodbek Abduvohid ugli
Tashkent State University of Economics
3rd year student of the Faculty of Economics
+998936401614
uldasevozodbek5@gmail.com

Abstract. Currently, the digital economy is considered as a driver of socio-economic progress and as a factor of economic growth of an innovative type. This study is devoted to an overview of the main concepts and key aspects of digital innovations, their distinctive features and characteristics are presented. The main trends and characteristics of digital transformation are considered, including the impact of technologies on the business environment, society and the economy.

The study identified the prerequisites for further development of a methodology in the field of assessing the digital maturity of industrial enterprises.

Keywords: innovation, digital technology, factors of digital technology, digital innovation, artificial intelligence, strategy measures to stimulate innovation

The development of modern society is accompanied by a transition from an industrial to an information-digital model of its existence. Digital technologies are gradually being introduced into all spheres of public life, forming new trends in their development. The introduction and promotion of digital technologies in society assumes that all major social processes (production, distribution, consumption) are inextricably linked with the generation and accumulation of information flows presented in digital form. New concepts such as "end-to-end information technologies", "digital transformation", "digital economy", "knowledge economy" are emerging. In today's conditions of global competition, innovative development of the country is almost impossible without the effective implementation and application of digital solutions in innovative activities. New digital technologies and platforms built on their basis allow optimizing the process of interaction between business entities, significantly accelerating the search for information on various aspects of scientific and technical activities and innovative activities, reducing the time for the implementation and commercialization of innovative and scientific and technical products.

Currently, there are two main industries in the field of digital technologies and solutions: 1) the information and communication industry, which creates technologies that use microelectronics to collect, store, process and transmit data; 2) the information technology industry, the result of which is services designed to facilitate the performance of the functions of collecting, converting and storing data and information electronically [1].

Among the main distinctive features of the digitalization of processes in the field of research and innovation activities, the following can be distinguished:

- the activities of business entities are concentrated around digital platforms that unite them into a single information environment, which allows for effective interaction;

- standardization and unification of information on the proposed engineering services and scientific, technical and innovative products, which allows for the identification of target groups of potential consumers;

- the possibility of interaction between developers of scientific and technical products and potential consumers through digital information and communication technologies, which accelerates the process of its implementation and commercialization.

Digital innovations are of great importance in the modern world, they transform business, lifestyle and society as a whole [2]. Digital innovations are processes or changes associated with the application of new digital technologies, such as information systems, the Internet, mobile devices, artificial intelligence and others. They can cover the creation of new digital products, services, business models, as well as the improvement of existing ones.

Key aspects of digital innovations include:

- increasing the efficiency of process automation and reducing costs in production;

- expanding the availability of technologies, including mobile devices;

- improving communication and information exchange;

- innovations in healthcare;

- transforming education through online education and expanding access to knowledge;

- developing artificial intelligence to automate and improve life.

- increasing sustainability and caring for the environment through resource management and reducing environmental impact.

Overall, digital innovations have a profound impact on all areas of life and have the potential to improve the quality of life and solve many global problems.

Research in the field of digital innovations is critical for a number of reasons:

- rapid technological development;

- economic significance;
- social impact;
- cybersecurity;
- innovative potential;
- legal and ethical issues;
- global nature of impact.

The difference between digital innovation and traditional innovation lies in the technologies and methods used to achieve new results. These include technological focus, speed and flexibility of change, scope of application of technologies, interactivity and connectivity, updates and maintenance.

Both types of innovation have their own value and can interact with each other. Digital innovation, however, is often characterized by a faster pace of development and the ability to create new markets and opportunities, while traditional innovation can be important in more stable and traditional areas.

Technology plays a key role in shaping digital innovation. Its roles include:

- 1) stimulating new ideas;
- 2) improving existing processes;
- 3) developing new solutions;
- 4) increasing accessibility and convenience;
- 5) creating new markets;
- 6) Changing business models;
- 7) Improving data security and protection;
- 8) Interactivity and personalization.

Technology is the engine for digital innovation, and the ability to integrate and use it to solve complex problems and improve people's lives is becoming increasingly important for companies, organizations, and society as a whole.

The integration of technologies and the multidisciplinary nature of digital innovation are key aspects in the modern world:

1. Multidisciplinary approach – digital innovation often requires the involvement of experts from different fields of knowledge, such as information technology, business, design, engineering, medicine, and others, which contributes to a more complete and deeper understanding of complex problems and the creation of innovations.

2. Integration of technologies – digital innovation often involves combining different technologies and platforms to create new products and services.

3. Cross-industry solutions – digital innovation can penetrate various industries and create new opportunities for cooperation and partnerships between companies from different fields.

4. Solving complex problems – many modern challenges, such as climate change and healthcare, require multidisciplinary and integrated approaches.

5. Flexibility and adaptability – multidisciplinary teams and integration of technologies provide flexibility and the ability to quickly respond to changing conditions in the market and society.

6. Quality of products and services – the integration of different technologies and knowledge leads to the creation of higher quality and more innovative products and services that can meet customer needs.

As digital innovation continues to evolve, both companies and society face a number of challenges, some of the most important of which include:

- Cybersecurity and data privacy
- Change management and adaptation
- Infrastructure and resources
- Data management and analytics
- Lack of skilled workers
- Legal and regulatory aspects
- Risk of dependence on tech giants
- Privacy and ethical concerns
- Inclusion and accessibility
- Environmental issues
- Threat to jobs [3]

Addressing these challenges requires a joint effort by companies, governments and society as a whole. It is important to develop strategies and policies that adhere to the principles of sustainable and responsible implementation of digital innovation.

In order to objectively assess their position in terms of digital development relative to competitors and the need to introduce innovations into their activities, local companies need to develop methods for assessing their digital maturity. Today, there is no single standard for this assessment and all companies are starting to engage in their own developments, but the principles for such an assessment are general, they include the following blocks:

1. "Digital culture - the level of organizational culture that supports the processes of continuous improvement and innovation, change management.

2. Personnel - compliance of personnel with the competencies of a civil servant necessary for successful work in the digital economy.

3. Processes - application of process management practices: process optimization methods, lean manufacturing, design thinking. Analysis, monitoring and continuous updating of processes.

4. Digital products - analysis of existing products and activities with them. Product - a solution to the user's need, carrying value for the latter.

5. Models - continuous updating of models, their validity and inclusion in activity processes.

6. Data – access to the necessary data in real time with the required level of security. Completeness and quality of data for decision-making.

7. Infrastructure and tools – access to modern digital infrastructure and ensuring operation on all types of devices”.

Thus, the development of a methodology for assessing the digital maturity of companies is an important tool for determining where the company is in the digital world and how it can improve its position by adapting to modern requirements and opportunities.

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